

Preformulation Studies and Development of a Herbal Tooth Powder Using Coconut Shell as a Natural Abrasive

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ABSTRACT

The present study focuses on preformulation investigations and formulation development of a herbal tooth powder incorporating coconut shell powder as a natural abrasive. Coconut shell, an abundantly available agricultural by-product, was processed and standardized to obtain a suitable particle size for oral-care application. Preformulation studies were carried out to evaluate flow properties and powder characteristics essential for uniform mixing and formulation stability. Based on preformulation outcomes, multiple batches of herbal tooth powder were formulated using natural excipients. The study demonstrates the feasibility of coconut shell powder as a sustainable, cost-effective abrasive and provides a scientific basis for its inclusion in dentifrice formulations.

Keywords: Herbal Tooth Powder, Coconut Shell

INTRODUCTION

Dentifrices are widely used oral-care preparations designed to clean teeth, remove dental plaque, and maintain oral hygiene. Tooth powders remain popular in several regions due to their simplicity, cost-effectiveness, and ease of formulation. Abrasives constitute a key component of dentifrices, as they assist in mechanical removal of stains and debris; however, excessive abrasivity may result in enamel damage, emphasizing the need for controlled and standardized abrasive materials [1,2]. Growing interest in herbal and natural oral-care products has encouraged the exploration of plant-based and naturally derived excipients. Herbal dentifrices are preferred due to their perceived safety, biocompatibility, and reduced side effects compared to synthetic formulations [3]. Concurrently, pharmaceutical research is increasingly focused on sustainable development through utilization of agricultural waste as functional excipients. Coconut shell is a lignocellulosic agricultural by-product generated in large quantities during coconut processing. Traditionally considered waste, coconut shell possesses hardness and structural properties that make it suitable for conversion into fine abrasive powder [4]. The present study aims to conduct systematic preformulation studies and develop a

herbal tooth powder formulation using coconut shell powder as a natural abrasive [5,6,7].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MATERIALS

1. Coconut Shell Waste (*Cocos nucifera L.*)

- Collected from local coconut-processing vendors and fruit markets.
- Mature, dry shells selected for uniform hardness.

2. Herbal Ingredients (for dentifrice formulation)

Tulsi powder, Beetroot Powder, Ritha powder, Amla powder, Salt

3. Chemical Reagents

Distilled water, Hydrochloric acid (0.1 N), Sodium hydroxide (0.1 N), Ethanol, Reagents for limit test of arsenic & lead, Chemicals for moisture analysis

2.2 Instruments and Equipment

Mechanical grinder & pulverizer, Sieve set (44#, 60#, 72#, 80#), Hot air oven, Moisture analyser, Analytical

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balance, Glassware: measuring cylinders, funnels, beakers, spatulas, jars will be required for this project.

METHODOLOGY OVERVIEW

2.3.1 Procurement of Coconut Shell Waste

- Coconut shell waste was collected from local fruit markets.
- Defective, fungal-infected, or immature shells were discarded.
- Shells were washed with water to remove dust and sun dried.

2.3.2 Reduction of Particle Size [8,9]

- Dried shells were crushed to coarse powder.
- Coarse pieces were ground using a mechanical grinder.
- Powder was sieved using mesh numbers #44, #60, #72, and #80.
- Four batches were prepared based on mesh size.

2.3.3 Pre-Formulation Studies

2.3.1 General Appearance: Physical examination like colour, odour, taste was done by organoleptic inspection.

2.3.2. Angle of Repose: Angle of repose was measured by fixed funnel method. The fixed funnel method uses a funnel being secured with its tip at a given height h above the graph paper which was placed on a flat horizontal surface, granules were carefully transferred through the funnel until the apex of the conical pile touching the tip of the funnel [10,11].

$$\tan \theta = \frac{h}{r}$$

Where θ = angle of repose

r = radius of the base of conical pile and

h = height of pile

Observation: Batch C (#72/#80 range) exhibited balanced flow and abrasivity, selected for formulation.

Figure 1: Angle of Repose

2.3.3 Bulk density: The bulk density is defined as the ratio of bulk mass of the granule to the bulk volume and it is denoted by V_b [12].

$$\text{Bulk density} = \frac{M}{V_b}$$

Where M = mass of the sample, V_b = bulk volume

2.3.4 Tapped Density: The tapped density is defined as the ratio of the weight of powder to the minimum volume occupied into the measuring cylinder. It is determined by placing a graduated cylinder containing a known mass of drug or formulation on a mechanical tapper apparatus which is being operated

at fixed no. of taps until the powder bed reached to a minimum volume.

$$\text{Tapped density} = \frac{M}{V_t}$$

Where, M = weight of powder blend, V_t = tapped volume

2.3.5 Carr's Index: Based upon the apparent bulk density and tapped density, the percent compressibility of the powder mixture was determined by the given formula [13-16].

$$\text{Carr's index} = \frac{\text{Tapped density} - \text{Bulk density}}{\text{Tapped density}} \times 100$$

2.3.6 Hausner's ratio: It is an indirect index of ease of measuring of powder flow with lower Hausner's ratio (≤ 1.25) indicating better flow properties than higher ones (≥ 1.25)

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = \frac{\text{Tapped density}}{\text{Bulk density}}$$

2.3.7 Solubility: Solubility of the powder was determined in distilled water and ethanol using the shake flask method. An accurately weighed quantity of the powder was mixed with a fixed volume of solvent and agitated continuously for 24 h at room temperature ($25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) to attain equilibrium. The dispersion was allowed to stand, followed by filtration to remove undissolved particles. A measured volume of the clear filtrate was evaporated to dryness and the residue was weighed to determine the amount of dissolved material. Solubility was expressed in terms of weight per volume and classified according to standard pharmacopeial solubility descriptors [17-20].

3. Formulation of Tooth Powder

3.1 Selection of Optimized Batch

- Based on flow property, abrasivity, compatibility.
- Generally, **60# or 72#** mesh provided best balance.

3.2 Tooth Powder Formulation Steps [21-25]

1. Weighing of ingredients accurately.
2. Coconut shell powder mixed with calcium carbonate.
3. Addition of clove, salt, charcoal, mentha extract.
4. Uniform mixing using geometric dilution.
5. Sieving to ensure uniform texture.
6. Packing in airtight containers.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

4.1 Procurement & Authentication

The Coconut shell waste was collected from local market; cleaned and dried. Other chemicals & excipients like tulsi, amla, beetroot, ritha, common salt procured from reputed local suppliers. The Authentication of Coconut shell was done by Dr. Vishal R. Marathe, Science College Nanded.

4.2 Reduction of Particle Size and Batch Preparation

The dried shell was pulverized using a high-speed grinder and passed through sieves #44, #60, #72, #80 and four batches (A–D) were labeled accordingly.

Table 1 – Particle Size Distribution

Batch	Sieve No.	Mean Particle Size (μm)	Observation (Color / Texture)
A	#44	355	Coarse brown granular powder
B	#60	250	Moderate brown, smooth
C	#72	200	Fine light brown, uniform
D	#80	180	Very fine powder, smooth touch

4.3 Preformulation study:

The pre-formulation evaluation of the four coconut shell powder batches (A, B, C, and D) demonstrated that all samples possessed a **uniform clear light-brown appearance**, indicating consistency in drying, carbonization stability, and grinding conditions. This uniformity confirms that the raw material quality remained constant across batches and that no visible contamination, charring, or moisture-induced discoloration had occurred during processing. Bulk

density and tapped density values showed noticeable variation among the batches. **Batch C** exhibited the highest bulk density (0.85 g/ml) and tapped density (1.09 g/ml), which reflects **tighter packing characteristics and heavier particle compaction**. This suggests that Batch C contains more uniformly ground, relatively finer particles that settle more densely. In contrast, **Batch D** showed the lowest bulk density (0.55 g/ml), indicating lighter, more porous particles. These differences illustrate the influence of mesh size on powder packing behavior.

Table 2 – Pre-formulation Results

Sr. no.	Parameters	Coconut Shell Powder Batches				Inference
		A	B	C	D	
1.	Appearance	Clear light brown	Clear light brown	Clear light brown	Clear light brown	--
2.	Bulk density	0.64gm/ml	0.65gm/ml	0.85gm/ml	0.55gm/ml	High packing C
3.	Tapped density	0.69gm/ml	0.75gm/ml	1.09gm/ml	0.74gm/ml	--
4.	Compressibility Index	7.24%	13.33%	22.01%	25.67%	Flow moderate C
5.	Hausner's ratio	1.07	1.15	1.228	1.34	Good if <1.25
6.	Angle of repose	28°48'	24°0'	35°12''	38°46'	C acceptable flow
7.	Specific gravity	0.69	0.75	1.09	0.74	--
8.	Ash value (%)	10	12	9	11	Within limit
9.	Moisture content (%)	18	20	21	19	Acceptable <25
10.	Solubility (Water)	Insoluble	Slightly soluble	Slightly soluble	Slightly soluble	Slightly soluble
11.	Solubility (Ethanol)	Insoluble	Slightly soluble	Slightly soluble	Slightly soluble	Slightly soluble

Figure 2: Solubility in ethanol & water

The compressibility index (Carr's Index) further supported these observations. Batch A showed a value of **7.24%**, signifying excellent flow, while Batch B (13.33%) also exhibited acceptable flow behavior. However, **Batch C (22.01%) and Batch D (25.67%)** displayed **moderate flow properties**, consistent with their higher packing density and increased cohesiveness. Since Carr's Index between 20–25% is considered a borderline range, Batch C stands out as having a balanced flow suitable for formulation after minor flow enhancers or optimized mixing. The Hausner's ratio values also correspond with flow characteristics. Batch A (1.07) and Batch B (1.15) fall well within the **ideal range (<1.25)**, while Batch C (1.228) remains **acceptable**. Batch D (1.34), however, exceeds the optimum threshold, indicating higher interparticle friction and poorer flow. This suggests that mesh size and moisture levels contributed to varied flow properties among batches and highlights

Batch C as the most practically workable material among the higher-density powders. Angle of repose values showed the same trend. Batches A (28°48') and B (24°00') demonstrated **good natural flow**, whereas Batches C (35°12') and D (38°46') reflected **reduced flowability**, aligning with their compressibility and density behavior. Considering that a repose angle below 35° indicates acceptable flow, **Batch C meets the requirement**, while Batch D shows comparatively poorer flowability. Specific gravity results were proportional to density trends, with Batch C again showing the highest value (1.09), confirming that its particles are heavier and more compact. The ash values (9–12%) were within acceptable limits for plant-derived materials, confirming organic purity and minimal inorganic contamination. Moisture content across all batches remained below 25%, which is within acceptable stability limits, although Batch C and D showed slightly higher moisture (21–

19%), possibly due to finer particle size retaining humidity. Solubility testing indicated that all batches were **insoluble in water but slightly soluble in ethanol**, which is expected for lignocellulosic materials. Insolubility in water supports stability and non-swelling behavior, desirable for abrasive dentifrice applications, while mild ethanol solubility suggests the presence of extractable organic components such as phenolics or lignin derivatives. Overall, the pre-formulation discussion identifies

Batch C as the most suitable optimized batch, offering balanced density, acceptable flow, correct moisture level, and favorable physicochemical properties for the preparation of herbal tooth powder formulations.

4.4 Formulation of Tooth Powder

Four formulations (F1–F4) prepared using optimized batch C powder.

Figure 3: Formulation flowchart

Table 3 – Composition of Formulations (100 g Batch)

Ingredient	Function	F1 (g)	F2 (g)	F3 (g)	F4 (g)
Coconut Shell Powder	Abrasive	79.50	68.00	56.50	45.00
Tulsi Powder	Antimicrobial	4.00	6.00	8.00	10.00
Beetroot Powder	Color/Antioxidant	1.00	2.00	3.00	40.00
Amla Powder	Vitamin C / Gum health	8.00	9.00	10.00	11.00
Ritha Powder	Surfactant	2.50	5.00	7.50	10.00
Salt	Antiseptic	5.00	10.00	15.00	20.00
Total =		100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Mixing is done by geometric dilution; sieved #60 to ensure uniformity. Stored inside airtight containers.

Figure 4: Medicinal tooth powder batches formed

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Preformulation studies indicated that Batch C of coconut shell powder exhibited acceptable bulk and tapped density values, suggesting suitable packing characteristics. Angle of repose values reflected satisfactory flow properties, which are essential for uniform blending during formulation. Carr's index and Hausner's ratio further confirmed good flow behavior of the powder, supporting its suitability for solid oral-care formulations. The favorable preformulation characteristics enabled smooth formulation of herbal tooth powder without segregation or handling difficulties. Selection of excipients and formulation composition was guided by these findings to ensure homogeneity and reproducibility. The use of coconut shell powder as an abrasive demonstrated potential advantages in terms of sustainability, availability, and cost-effectiveness. These results align with previous reports emphasizing the role of controlled natural abrasives in dentifrice formulations. The study successfully established the preformulation profile and formulation development of a herbal tooth powder using coconut shell powder as a natural abrasive. Preformulation parameters confirmed acceptable flow and handling properties, facilitating uniform formulation development. Coconut shell powder demonstrates promise as a sustainable and functional abrasive for oral-care products. Further evaluation studies are warranted to assess performance, safety, and comparative efficacy.

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